

Article

PRETCO: An English Test for Vocational and Technical College Students

Yongjie Chen

Shanghai Jiao Tong University, China

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Abstract

In China, vocational and technical colleges account for more than half of its institutions of higher education. For most students in these colleges, English is compulsory. This creates one of China's largest English learning bodies. The paper deals with the Practical English Test for Colleges (PRETCO), a nation-wide standardized English test specially designed for non-English majors of vocational and technical colleges. Specifically, it first focuses on its purpose, length, and administration. Then, it describes its development and introduces its components and format at length. It also describes test takers' performance in the test. Finally, it provides an overall evaluation of the test.

Keywords

PRETCO, purpose, format, non-English majors, vocational and technical colleges

1 Introduction

Higher vocational education is an important part of higher education in China. According to the Ministry of Education (2021), there were 1,468 three-year vocational and technical colleges in 2020, which account for more than half of China's institutions of higher education. In most of these vocational and technical colleges, English is taught to non-English majors as a compulsory course. As a nation-wide standardized English test specially designed for non-English majors in these colleges, the Practical English Test for Colleges (PRETCO) has been around for about two decades. This paper is intended to describe its purpose, administration, background to its development, and test design, and provides an overall evaluation.

2 PRETCO

The purpose of the test is to assess Chinese vocational college students' English proficiency in using English as a practical tool to handle everyday and career-related communication and to ensure that Chinese undergraduates of vocational and technical colleges reach the required English levels illustrated

in the *Basic English Curriculum Requirements of Higher Vocational and Technical Education* (Ministry of Education, 2000). Based on the teaching objectives and course arrangements in the curriculum requirements, PRETCO comprises of three sub-tests: PRETCO-Level A, PRETCO-Level B and PRETCO-Oral Test. The test is an internal one, which means only students who are currently studying at these colleges can take it. Currently, it is the second largest test after the College English Test (CET) in tertiary education in China. The candidature is about 3 million each year for the written tests and about 40,000 for the oral test.

The test is administered by the Testing Committee of PRETCO (see details of its composition in Section 4 Description below). The written tests of the two levels are held twice a year near the end of each semester, each test lasting 120 minutes. PRETCO-Oral Test is a computer-assisted test, which is also held twice a year about one month before the written tests. The oral test lasts approximately 20 minutes.

PRETCO test scores are reported to the participating colleges. Both the written test and the oral test are criterion-referenced. For the written tests, the full score is 100 for Level A and Level B respectively. Test takers who have scored 60 or above in the written tests receive a certificate from the Testing Committee of PRETCO. Their level of performance in each of the tests is indicated either by “pass” (score between 60 and 79.5) or by “excellent” (score 80 or above). As for the oral test, the full raw score is 16. Those who pass the test receive a separate certificate on which their level of performance is indicated either by “pass” (score between 9.5 and 12.5) or “excellent” (score 13 or above).

The test is administered by the Testing Committee of PRETCO, based in Shanghai. The test fees vary from province to province, ranging from 15 RMB (about \$2US) to 40 RMB (about \$6 US). The average fee is RMB 20 for the written test or for the oral test.

3 Development

Higher education in China generally falls into two sectors: higher education, and higher vocational and technical education. The focus of instruction in these two different sectors is different and so are the curriculums. Graduates from higher education, usually from a four-year college, are awarded a bachelor's degree while those from the three-year vocational and technical education sector usually are awarded a diploma. However, before 1993, there was no national syllabus of English instruction for three-year vocational or technical colleges in China. In most cases these colleges used the same teaching syllabus and course books designed for four-year universities and colleges for English instruction, but with lower requirements. In 1993, the Ministry of Education issued *Basic English Curriculum Requirements of Higher Vocational and Technical Education*, focusing on teaching English for practical use. In 2000, the new syllabus, *Basic English Curriculum Requirements of Higher Vocational and Technical Education* further emphasized that the English teaching purpose of vocational and technical colleges is to develop students' proficiency in the use of the language for their future work. The requirements state that given students' English proficiency when they enter college, English instruction requirements are divided into two levels: Level A and Level B. Level A is the standard requirement while Level B is the minimum requirement for students whose English proficiency is relatively lower when they are admitted to college. The requirements also state that the assessment of students' English proficiency should focus on their use of English to cope with everyday and career related communication.

To implement the requirements, a special research group was formed to explore the assessment of English instruction of vocational and technical colleges and to build a test bank against the teaching goals and course requirements prescribed by the Ministry of Education in *Basic English Curriculum Requirements of Higher Vocational and Technical Education* (2000). The test bank was adopted by several hundred colleges and was well received. Based on the revised test bank, the Practical English Test for Colleges was first launched in 1998 in eight provinces as a pilot test, and in 1999 it expanded to

13 provinces. In 2000, the test was formally launched in 26 provinces to assess vocational and technical college students' English proficiency. In 2001, the testing committee of the *Practical English Test for Colleges* was established. This committee is mainly composed of English testing experts and professors from different vocational and technical colleges. Some come from 4-year colleges and universities. Its main tasks are to develop test criteria for assessing students' English proficiency, design and provide test papers. In 2005, PRETCO-Oral Test was launched nationwide.

Based on the *Basic English Curriculum Requirements of Higher Vocational and Technical Education* (2000), the testing committee published *The Exam Syllabus and Sample Tests of Practical English Test for Colleges* (Written Test) (2000, 2014) and *The Exam Syllabus and Sample Tests of PRETCO Oral Test* (2004, 2014).

In 2014, the written tests underwent a major revision with more emphasis on listening comprehension. According to the revised exam syllabus (PRETCO Testing Committee, 2014), the listening comprehension of Level A accounts for 20 percent of the total score instead of 15 percent in the former test. For Level B, the listening part increases from 15 percent to 24 percent of the total score. A new section (spot dictation) was added to Level A, and a new section consisting of conversations added to Level B. The number of multiple-choice questions on vocabulary and structure was reduced.

4 Description

PRETCO consists of three sub-tests, that is, PRETCO Level A, PRETCO Level B and PRETCO Oral Test. An overview of these tests is provided below.

4.1 Written tests

Each of the written tests consists of five parts, that is, listening comprehension, vocabulary and structure, reading comprehension, translation and writing.

4.1.1 Listening

Each of the listening parts of Level A and Level B of the written tests consists of four sections. Its purpose is to assess students' ability to understand questions, short dialogues, short conversations and short passages. In Level A, the first section is five short dialogues and, after listening to each dialogue, students should decide on the correct answer from four choices that are provided. Both the dialogues and questions are spoken only once. The second section consists of two short conversations. Each conversation is followed by four choices and both the conversations and questions are spoken twice. Section 3 is a passage printed in the test paper with some words or phrases missing. Students listen to the passage twice and then fill in the blanks, using either the exact words or phrases they heard or their own words. For Section 4, students listen to a passage and then complete the answers to the five questions using no more than three words as required by the directions. Questions and incomplete answers are printed in the test paper. Both the passage and questions are spoken twice.

In Level B, the first section is "questions and responses". Students listen to a question twice and then decide on the correct answer from the four choices given. The questions are spoken twice. The second section is "short dialogues". Both the dialogues and questions are spoken twice. The third section consists of two short conversations. Each conversation is followed by four choices and both the conversation and questions are spoken twice. For Section 4, students listen to a short passage three times. The passage is printed on the test paper with some words or phrases missing. Students are asked to fill in the missing parts with the exact words they heard.

The speed of the recorded speaking is 120 wpm for Level A and 100 wpm for Level B. This part accounts for 20 percent of the total score and is 20 minutes long for Level A, and 24 percent of the total score and is 25 minutes long for Level B. (Examples of Section C and Section D of Level A are provided in Appendix 1.)

4.1.2 Vocabulary and structure

This part consists of 15 items for both Level A and Level B, among which 10 are in the form of MC questions, and the other five items are in the form of gap filling. The purpose of this part is to assess students' ability to use English correctly. This part accounts for 15 percent of the whole score. The time to complete this part is 10 minutes. Figure 1 below presents sample items from Level A.

Figure 1

Sample Items from PRETCO Level A Test

-
23. The new drug will not be put on the market _____ it has proved safe on humans.
- A) when C) since
B) until D) if
26. The proposal _____ at the meeting now is of great importance to our department.
- A) being discussed C) having discussed
B) to be discussing D) discussing
31. When he came to the city for the second visit ten years later, he found it completely (change) _____.
32. Working from home is flexible and beneficial not only to the employees but also to the (employ) _____.
-

4.1.3 Reading

The reading part of both levels consists of five tasks. This part aims to assess students' ability to understand and use the information in the written passages. It contributes to 35 percent of the total score, of which 20 percent is for tasks 1-2 and 5 percent for each of tasks 3, 4 and 5 respectively. The time to complete this part is 40 minutes for Level A and 35 minutes for Level B. For this part, students are asked to read 4 passages, and then do the MC questions, gap filling and short answer questions. Task 4 is a matching question task, in which students are asked to find the English items equivalent to those given in Chinese. Most of the passages and sentences in the test are of authentic language and adapted from different sources like notices, advertisements, business letters, workplace posters and company profiles. The length of passages varies from 150 words to 250 words according to the task type. (Appendix 2 provides sample reading comprehension tasks of the tests.)

4.1.4 Translation

The translation part is designed to assess students' ability to translate (from English to Chinese). Both levels consist of two sections. The first section consists of four English sentences, each of which is followed by three different Chinese versions. Students are asked to choose the best version. The second section is a paragraph. The paragraph is about 75 words long for Level B and about 65 words long for Level A. This part accounts for 15 percent of the total score. The time to complete this part is 25 minutes. (Appendix 3 provides a sample paragraph for translation.)

4.1.5 Writing

The writing part of the test is to assess students' ability in simple professional communication. Using the information given in Chinese, students are asked to do a piece of practical writing such as a business letter, email, memo, notice, resume, advertisement and application. The writing task of Level B is slightly different from that of Level A in that students are required to fill in five blanks with the information provided in Chinese. There are no word limits for the writing. The time limit for this part is 25 minutes. It accounts for 15 percent of the total score. (Appendix 4 provides a sample writing task of Level B.)

4.2 Oral test

PRETCO Oral Test is a separate computer-assisted test meant to assess students' oral English proficiency in business-oriented situations. The test developers assume that those who have passed the test are able to handle simple daily and business communication in English.

According to *The Exam Syllabus and Sample Tests of PRETCO Oral Test* (2004, 2014), test-takers should be able to use English in the following situations:

- 1) Daily communication:
 - a. Function: introducing, greeting, expressing thanks, apologizing, saying good-bye, giving directions, and etc.
 - b. Topics: weather, study, hobbies, food, health, and etc.
- 2) Business-oriented communication:
 - a. General activities: meeting and seeing off, planning schedules, arranging business activities, making reservations, helping others to do shopping, touring and seeing a doctor, etc.
 - b. General business activities: introducing a company, demonstrating a product, business negotiation, and etc.

The oral test contains 4 parts: reading aloud, question and answer, Chinese-English interpretation and presentation. Each part accounts for 25 percent of the total score. Table 1 lays out the components of the oral test.

Table 1

Oral Test Components

Part	Task	Time	Score
Warm up	Three questions	1'30''(1 minute and 30 seconds)	
Part I	Reading aloud	3' (including 1 minute and 15 seconds preparation)	4
Part II	Question and answer	2' (including 1 minute preparation)	4
Part III	Chinese-English interpretation	3'(including 1 minute preparation)	4
Part IV	Presentation	4'(including 1 minute and 30 seconds preparation)	4
Total	4	12'(including 4 minutes 45 seconds preparation)	16

4.2.1 Reading aloud

In this part, students are given a short text of about 120 words. The text is adapted from an announcement, a speech, or a monologue. Students' performance is evaluated based on the accuracy of pronunciation, intonation and fluency. A sample text is provided in Appendix 5.

4.2.2 Question and answer

In this part, students have two tasks. First, they will see a poster on the screen, such as an advertisement, a notice or table with some information missing. After one-minute preparation, they will ask three questions about the missing information. During the preparation, they are not allowed to make any notes. Then, they will see the complete poster and listen to a short recorded conversation with some parts missing. Their task is to complete the conversation by answering the questions according to the poster. (Appendix 6 provides the sample tasks of this part.)

Students' performance is evaluated based on the accuracy of their questions and answers.

4.2.3 Chinese-English interpretation

In this part, students are given a short passage of about 100 Chinese characters. After one-minute preparation, they are required to complete their oral interpretation of the passage within 2 minutes. Students' translation is evaluated based on accuracy, completeness and target language quality. A sample passage for interpretation is provided in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2

A Sample Passage for Interpretation from Chinese to English

我们是一家生产汽车玻璃的企业。我们公司成立于2012年，现有员工300多人。我们的产品畅销国内外，深受客户欢迎。为了公司发展需要，今年我们计划招聘15名员工。如果你想了解更多有关本公司的情况，请访问我们的网站。

4.2.4 Presentation

In this part, students are given a chart on the screen with the task given below in English. After one minute and 30 seconds' preparation, they are required to give a presentation of 2 minutes and 30 seconds. During the preparation, they are not allowed to make any notes. They will first describe the chart as shown in the example, and then account for some phenomena. They are also asked to give their own view about some issue related to the information in the chart.

Student's performance is evaluated based on accuracy and fluency in presenting the information in the chart, the explanation of the data and expression of personal view. Figure 3 below presents a sample chart.

Figure 3

A Sample Chart

5 Test Taker Performance

PRETCO test scores are reported to the participating colleges about one month after the test. According to the test scores for the written test held in December 2018 (Y. Chen, 2019), the average pass rate of the written test varied considerably from province to province due to students' differing English proficiency. The highest provincial/ municipal average pass rate was 64.9% with a mean of 64.8%. The lowest pass rate was 15.1% with a mean of 45%. The same held true for Level B. The highest provincial/ municipal average pass rate was 53.2% while the lowest was 29.1%. Students performed better in the reading comprehension section than in the other sections while they did poorly in the section of vocabulary and structure and the writing section.

For the oral test, the average pass rate has been consistently around 55% for several years (Y. Chen, 2019). Students perform best in the reading aloud section, scoring about 2.93 (out of the full score 4) on average. The mean for the Chinese-English translation section is about 1.97 (out of a full score of 4) while the mean for the presentation section is about 1.95 (out of a full score of 4).

6 Appraisal

Since PRETCO's first administration, a considerable amount of research has been conducted on its validity and washback effect, as the following section briefly outlines.

6.1 Validity

Research conducted on the validity of the reading and listening parts of PRETCO (Ji 2011; Liu 2013; Wan 2015; Wei 2011; Zhang 2005) indicates that these parts of the test are reliable and valid. Liu (2013) analysed the listening parts of ten PRETCO Level B papers, interviewing approximately 300 test takers. She reported that the listening part had high construct validity (2013). Wan (2015) interviewed 151 test takers and 20 teachers, reporting that 83% of test takers and 93% of teachers found the listening part of PRETCO-Level B to have high face validity. Similar findings emerged from Wei's (2011) and Ji's (2011) studies. In both studies, the reading part of PRETCO Level B was considered to have high validity (Ji 2011; Wei 2011). In an investigation of criterion-related validity, construct validity, content validity and

face validity of the reading comprehension part of PRETCO Level A, Zhang (2005) reported that test takers' reading comprehension proficiency levels – as ranked by test scores – very closely matched their English teachers' assessments. In an exploration of the validity of rating criteria of PRETCO Oral Test by analyzing ratings via Multifaceted Rasch Analysis, Yang and Quan's (2016) findings indicated that the PRETCO Oral Test rating criteria were able to differentiate test takers of different English proficiency. Further research needs to be conducted on the validity of the other parts of PRETCO such as the writing and translation parts, as certain researchers (Liu Qin & Ouyang, 2013; Yu, 2015; Xiao, 2017) have suggested.

6.2 Washback and impact

A number of studies have explored the washback effect of PRETCO (H. Chen, 2017; He, 2009; Li, 2013; Li, 2016; Liu, 2013; Lu, 2010; Mao, 2010; Nan, 2011; Pu, 2011; Wang, 2007) In studies employing surveys, classroom observation and interviews, research findings indicated that – as the only large-scale test for vocational students in China –PRETCO has produced positive washback on students: improving their English learning motivation, enabling them to learn about their future needs in English proficiency and helping them establish their English goals. Most teachers reported a positive attitude toward PRETCO, believing that the test offers them a valid and reliable measure of their students' English language proficiency. At the same time, PRETCO has, however, some negative washback effects on students and teachers. It has created learning pressure on students, causing some test takers to have anxiety, for example. In part this is due to the fact that some students only learn English for the purpose of passing the test, and consequently some teachers spend too much classroom time preparing students for the test. On the whole, however, the available evidence would suggest that the positive washback of PRETCO far outweighs its negative washback.

With the issue of *China's Standards of English Language Ability* (CSE) by the National Education Examinations Authority (2018), the challenge facing PRETCO test developers involves how to relate the test to CSELA while implementing the requirements set in the *Basic English Curriculum Requirements of Higher Vocational and Technical Education*.

7 Conclusion

The Practical English Test for Colleges (PRETCO) is an English test specially designed for non-English majors of vocational and technical colleges in China. It has been outlined in the current paper – starting with a brief introduction to the background and development of PRETCO, a test for non-English majors in China's vocational and technical colleges. A description of the test's components and format with samples was provided. Finally, research findings were presented regarding the validity and washback effect of the test.

Appendix 1

Samples of Level A, Section C and Section D

Section C

Good evening, Ladies and Gentlemen. A warm welcome to you all to this reception. First, I'd like to say a few words about tonight's 11. We shall begin with a talk by Professor Richard Johnson from London. This will be followed by a question and answer period. You will be free to 12 with the professor. At about 8 o'clock tonight when the talk finishes, the reception will 13, and we have prepared some chocolates, drinks and fruits outside for you. The professor is taking 14 home tonight. Although we

would like to have him here longer with us, we have to 15 that he leaves here by 8:30.
(11. program(me) 12. exchange ideas 13. begin 14. his flight 15. make sure)

Section D

16. What does the speaker think of his working conditions?

He thinks that the working conditions are _____.

17. How many hours does the speaker work every week?

_____.

18. How does the speaker spend his holiday in winter?

He usually takes one week to _____.

19. What system did the company introduce last year?

It introduced a flexible _____ system.

20. When can the speaker start his work in the morning?

Any time between _____ in the morning.

(Script: I'm a full-time white collar worker. I should say my working conditions are really good. The working hours are very reasonable. I work 38 hours a week, from Monday to Friday. I get a four-week holiday with pay. I always go on a two-week vacation in the summer and I usually take another week to travel abroad in the winter. That still leaves a few days if I want to take time off for something else. We're even allowed to take unpaid leave if it's really necessary. Our company introduced a flexible working time system last year, so I can start any time between 8 and 9 in the morning, and sometimes I can leave as early as 4 o'clock in the afternoon.)

Appendix 2

Sample Reading Comprehension Tasks

Task 2, Level B

Notice to Customers

Dear Customers,
Please be advised that from Monday, 3rd October parking at the Breakwater Terminal is **\$7.00 per day**, or part thereof.

Tickets and longer parking permits are available for purchase from our ticketing counters inside the Breakwater Terminal or from the car park attendant.

Enquire about our Monthly Saver Parking Permit or our Yearly Super Saver Parking Permit & start saving now!

Thank you and have a great day!
Yours Sincerely,
SeaLink QLD Management

45. The new parking charge starts _____.
- A) from October 3 B) from next week
C) from next year D) from October 1
46. The new parking charge for per day is _____.
- A) 3 dollars B) 4 dollars
C) 7 dollars D) 14 dollars
47. Customers can buy a parking ticket _____,
- A) online C) from a car park attendant
B) from a post office D) from the ticketing counter in a store

Task 2, Level A

<p>Safety Tips</p> <p><i>Keeping Streeterville a Safe Neighborhood</i></p> <p>Safety at Home</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Keep your doors and windows locked when you are not home Report any burned out lights to building manager Know the location of all fire exits and stairwells in your building <p>Safety On the Street</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stay alert, aware, and walk with confidence Carry purses and wallets close to your body Carry your keys separate from your purse/briefcase Carry your ID with emergency contact information Don't allow your vision to be blocked by clothing, hats, or items that you are carrying Consider carrying a whistle to use when you observe trouble Avoid walking alone, especially at night If walking alone, make sure someone knows where and when you will be arriving at your destination Avoid wearing headphones when walking alone Choose routes that are well used, well lit, and safe Plan your route in advance and vary your route if possible If walking a long distance, turn around at least once on each block to ensure you aren't being followed <p>Safety When Parking</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Close all windows Lock your doors Secure personal belongings out of sight Park in a well-lit area <p>Safety On The CTA</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use best-lit stops to get on and off bus At night, sit near CTA driver <p>When to Call 311</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To report streetlight outage To report graffiti For general questions To file a police report for minor damage to, or theft of property To report conditions that make crime possible <p>When to Call 911</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> If you see someone who needs medical attention To report unattended children To report someone aggressively peddling If you or someone near you is in eminent danger To report suspicious activity <p>Streeterville Organization of Active Residents 244 East Pearson Street, Suite 102 Chicago, IL 60611</p>	<p>CTA (Chicago Transit Authority) 芝加哥市公交系统</p> <p>burned out light 烧坏的灯泡</p> <p>whistle 哨子</p> <p>outage (电力) 断供</p>
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41. When you see a burned-out light, you should _____.
- A) ask a repairperson to fix it B) replace it with a new light
C) report it to the building manager D) find out the cause of the trouble
42. When parking your car, you are advised to park it _____.
- A) in a well-lit area B) near your house
C) in a public parking lot D) in your own garage
43. When taking a CTA bus at night, you are advised to sit _____.
- A) next to the door B) near the driver
C) on the left side of the bus D) at the back of the bus
44. According to the poster, when walking alone on the street, you should _____.
- A) always take a whistle with you B) keep your keys in your briefcase
C) avoid wearing headphones D) put your ID card in your pocket
45. According to the poster, you should call 911 when _____.

- A) you have lost something important B) you have seen a suspicious activity
C) you have difficulty finding your way home D) you have seen any burned-out streetlights

Task 3, Level A

Deutsche Bahn AG

Deutsche Bahn (DB) AG was founded in 1994. Today, it is one of the world's leading passenger and logistics (物流) companies and operates in 130 countries.

Every day about 290,000 employees provide passenger transportation and logistics services for customers around the world, as well as controlling and operating the related transport networks in rail, land, ocean, and air transport. In the 2010 financial year, DB AG posted revenues (总收入) of about 34.4 billion euros (欧元).

The company's railway activities in Germany -- with about seven million passengers and 1,138,000 tons of goods transported every day -- are its core business. Moreover, every day DB transports more than two million customers by bus. And every day DB AG operates over 26,000 train trips on its modern 33,000 kilometer long track network. DB's main strategy, in addition to increasing its international activities, is to link together all modes of transport and building new travel and logistics chains worldwide.

<p>Deutsche Bahn (DB) AG A passenger and logistics company</p> <p>Year of founding: 1994</p> <p>Number of staff: about <u> 46 </u></p> <p>Services offered:</p> <p>1) providing <u> 47 </u> and logistics services</p> <p>2) controlling and <u> 48 </u> the related transport networks</p> <p>Revenues of 2010: about 34.4 billion euros</p> <p>Daily railway activities in Germany:</p> <p>1) transporting about <u> 49 </u> and 1,138,000 tons of goods</p> <p>2) operating over 26,000 <u> 50 </u></p>
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Appendix 3

Sample Level A Paragraph Translation

65. Over two-thirds of Americans now book their flights online. But when is the best time to book to get a cheap flight? Flying on Wednesday is a good way to save money: you'll find emptier and cheaper seats. If you can't avoid flying on a weekend, at least BOOK your flight on Wednesday; airlines tend to raise their fares on Friday and bring them back down on Monday. Another suggestion is to book your flight after the 7th of every month.

Appendix 4

Sample Level B Writing Task

假定你叫王洪，拟在某酒店举办一个会议。请根据下列内容填写登记表。
内容：

1. 入住时间：2012年6月25日，退房时间：2012年6月29日；
2. 预定房间：单人房；房间数量20间；
3. 付款方式：现金
4. 联系电话：010-799**090，传真：010-799**090；
5. 电子邮箱：wanghong7080@163.com
6. 特别要求：
 - 1) 会议共20人参加，在酒店享用早、中、晚餐；
 - 2) 要求可以在房间上网；
 - 3) 6月26日至6月28日租用酒店会议室一间，需计算机、投影仪等设备。

Reservation Form	
Name:	<u> (1) </u>
Check in:	<u> (2) </u>
Check out:	June 29th, 2012
Room type:	Single Room
Number of rooms reserved:	<u> (3) </u>
Payment:	Cash
Tel. number:	<u> (4) </u>
Fax number:	010-799**090
Email:	<u> (5) </u>
Special Requests:	_____

[投影仪 projector]

Appendix 5

Sample Reading Aloud Text

Good afternoon, everybody.

On behalf of the organizing committee, I'd like to welcome you all to this International Conference on Health and Environment.

Scientific research leads to a better understanding and knowledge of environment issues. New scientific knowledge may lead to new applications. So it is important not only to protect our environment but also ensure that it is safe and healthy for present and future generations.

This conference has attracted 220 participants from 61 countries. We have invited 6 key-note speakers. The subjects range widely, from quality control, environment protection, food safety, to new technologies. I am sure these topics will provide you with a wealth of information and many opportunities for discussion.

Appendix 6

Sample Question and Answer Part Tasks

Task One:

Sweet Berry Farm

Location: **Question 1**
(Just 10-minute drive from town.)

Strawberry Picking
Picking schedule: 7am-5pm, Monday-Friday
Picking season: Early June -- Early July
Payment: cash only

Café RED
Business Hours: **Question 2**
Air-conditioned and farm-style

Free Guided Farm Tours
Time: 11am, Monday -- Friday
Bookings required: on the website

For more information, visit our website.
Website: **Question 3**

Question 1: Question 2: Question 3:

Task Two:

Sweet Berry Farm

Location: 915 Mitchell's Lane
(Just 10-minute drive from town.)

Strawberry Picking
Picking schedule: 7am-5pm, Monday-Friday
Picking season: Early June -- Early July
Payment: cash only

Café RED
Business Hours: 9am-3pm, 7 days
Air-conditioned and farm-style

Free Guided Farm Tours
Time: 11am, Monday -- Friday
Bookings required: on the website

For more information, visit our website.
Website: www.sweetberry.com

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Yongjie Chen is a professor of English at the Foreign Languages School of Shanghai Jiao Tong University, China. His main academic interests include second language acquisition, material development and evaluation, language research methodology and testing.